

BRINGING STORIES TO LIFE: ENHANCING STUDENT'S COMPREHENSION IN TEACHING NOVEL THROUGH ANIMATION

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ABSTRACT

Engaging students in novel reading continues to be a challenge in secondary education, particularly when traditional teaching methods are used. These approaches often lead to low levels of comprehension and participation. To address this issue, a classroom-based study was conducted to enhance Grade 10 students' understanding and interest in learning novels by incorporating animation. It involved 35 students from a public school in Ozamiz City during the 2024–2025 academic year. Using a quantitative method, data were collected through a researcher-developed assessment given before and after the animation-based instruction was introduced. Before the intervention, most students scored below the satisfactory level—11 fell under the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category, 8 were rated "Fairly Satisfactory," and only 4 reached the "Very Satisfactory" level. Not a single student achieved an "Outstanding" score, indicating low engagement with traditional teaching methods. However, after animation was implemented, student performance improved significantly. Twenty-three students reached the "Very Satisfactory" level, five were rated "Satisfactory," and one student achieved an "Outstanding" score. The increase in performance was statistically significant, showing that the use of animation had a strong, positive effect on both comprehension and engagement. The study concludes that using animation in teaching novels can be highly effective, as it fosters a more inclusive, engaging, and lively classroom atmosphere. The use of animation in instruction not only enhances students' understanding of literary texts but also fosters increased classroom participation. Based on these findings, it is recommended that educators consider integrating animation and other creative teaching strategies to enrich students' learning experiences and improve their academic performance in Filipino literature.

Keywords: *animation, comprehension, engagement, Filipino literature, novel, instructional strategy*

CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

The teaching of literature often faces challenges in capturing the interest of 21st-century learners, who are more visually and digitally oriented. Prioritizing students' interest and understanding is essential, as it not only deepens their appreciation for literature but also promotes active engagement and critical thinking. However, teachers and learners faced a number of challenges (Mubita and Mwanza, 2020). One of the key challenges is the declining attention span of students when exposed to purely text-based materials. Enhancing students' interest and understanding is a key priority in education because it not only fosters a deeper appreciation for literature but also encourages active engagement and critical thinking. Therefore, to develop student's comprehension and understanding, engaging them with innovative methods, such as interactive storytelling and multimodal resources is essential (Trihastutie, 2023).

However, research has shown that many students today lose interest in literature when it is taught using only text-based materials. Animations can be powerful multimedia tools for engaging students, as they help simplify complex concepts through visual representation offering a more accessible alternative to traditional, text-heavy instruction (Feigenson, 2010). Students in the 21st century are more used to visuals, technology, and interactive activities, which makes it harder for them to stay focused on traditional teaching methods. Visual aids have proven effective in enhancing students' understanding, as shown by the significantly improved post-assessment scores in the experimental group. Additionally, students were noticeably more attentive when audio-visual materials were used (Ho et al., 2017). Teachers must identify strategies and methods that align with their students' learning levels, while also actively engaging them and capturing their attention (Rone et al., 2023).

In recent years, the significance of teaching literature has been increasingly recognized. It contributes to cultivating essential 21st-century skills, including creativity, emotional understanding, and global perspective, underscoring the need for a more comprehensive approach to education in today's interconnected society. However, a lack of effective teaching in literature will lead to disinterest, limited critical thinking skills, and a weaker connection to cultural and moral lessons. That's why effective teaching by not just merely using text-based concepts in literature is essential, as teaching using audio visual aids, makes the learning process more effective and delivers knowledge in greater

depth and detail (Rasul et al., 2011). Research findings from the review indicate that audio-visual media is highly effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes, students' participation and understanding in learning (Awalidinna and Utama, 2024).

Teaching literature is important because it helps students think critically and understand deeply by exploring different perspectives and learning from others' experiences. Similarly, audio-visual learning, which mimics human perception by integrating sight and hearing, has gained prominence in recent years for its ability to enhance comprehension and communication through a combination of audio and visual modalities (Wei et al., 2022). Through videos, it gaze guidance, the recipients' allocation of attention (Boy et al., 2020). Video media is an effective and accurate tool for conveying messages, enhancing students' understanding by presenting material in an engaging and visually appealing format. By using video media, educators can deliver content more effectively, helping students grasp concepts through dynamic and illustrative examples. Additionally, learning through videos fosters interest and motivates students to stay attentive, making lessons more impactful and enjoyable.

In addition, incorporating animations and multimedia tools in teaching literature offers an innovative solution to the difficulties students encounter when engaging with traditional text-based materials. By utilizing visual aids such as animations and videos, this approach fosters a more dynamic and engaging learning experience, enhancing students' comprehension of literary concepts. It also makes the learning process more enjoyable and interesting for students (Regina & Rajasekaran, 2023). Learning without audio-visual aids tends to discourage students, while incorporating such aids makes the class more engaging and interactive. Audio-visual tools enable teachers to convey lessons more effectively and capture students' interest (Audio-Visual, 2024). This approach helps bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and the needs of modern learners, promoting deeper comprehension, critical thinking, and meaningful connections to cultural and moral lessons. Additionally, the effectiveness of these strategies will be assessed in enhancing students' performance and engagement with literature, ensuring the use of methods that are both creative and meaningful (Widahyu, 2021).

The researcher noticed a clear gap in previous studies regarding the comprehensive integration of animation or audio-visual materials in teaching literature. Additionally, previous research has not explored how the use of animation and audio-visual aids specifically affects students' emotional connection to literary characters and themes. This area includes several unexplored aspects that have recently gained attention in other fields (Salamea et al., 2023; Baron et al., 2023). Further investigation into the use of animation and audio-visual tools in literature teaching is needed to better understand why these methods are not consistently incorporated into literature instruction (Miles, 2017).

This research aims to enhance literature teaching by integrating animation and audio-visual presentations, bringing stories to life and fostering a more engaging learning experience. It focuses on Junior High School students, particularly covering topics such as mythology, stories, legends, and novels. Although this study focuses on a specific group of participants and topics, the strategy could potentially be applied to other lessons, subjects, or schools if it proves effective. The importance of this research lies in its potential to deepen students' understanding of literary texts and themes enabling them to connect with the material in a more meaningful way. By incorporating animation and audio-visual presentations, the study seeks to capture students' attention, improve comprehension, and promote active engagement. This method not only makes learning more dynamic and interactive but also nurtures students' appreciation for literature, creativity, and critical thinking, ultimately inspiring a love for reading and storytelling.

STRATEGY

The the teaching of novel through animation strategy is designed to transform literature instruction during the 2024–2025 school year by integrating animation to deepen students' understanding of literary texts. Through the use of animated visuals, this strategy clarifies complex themes, characters, and events, fostering a stronger connection to the material and enhancing student engagement. Animation serves as a practical tool for making abstract ideas more accessible and memorable.

This strategy promotes collaborative learning by encouraging students to work in groups to create animated representations of literary scenes, characters, or themes. During the process, students engage in thoughtful discussions, critically analyze the text, and express their interpretations creatively through visual storytelling. It supports diverse learning styles, particularly benefiting visual learners, while enhancing retention by reinforcing key concepts through repeated interaction with the material. By requiring teamwork, it facilitates the development of essential skills among students like communication, collaboration, and problem-solving. Ultimately, this approach makes literature more accessible, engaging, and memorable by blending traditional analysis with creative and interactive methods.

Studies have shown that audio-visual materials can greatly enhance the effectiveness of instruction students' learning of grammar and vocabulary (Salamea & Fajardo, 2023). They also highlight the value of animation in fostering critical thinking, as it encourages learners to view ideas from multiple perspectives and express them visually. Moreover,

studies have shown that animation-based video modeling is an effective approach for improving the development of daily living skills (Yalçın & Arslantaş, 2023).

Additionally, the group-based nature of teaching novel through animation strengthens teamwork and communication as students collaborate to produce animated content. To ensure success, students must actively engage in the process and possess the necessary technical skills for creating animations. Potential challenges could arise if students struggle with the technology or lack interest in the group work. To overcome these barriers, teachers will offer guidance on using animation tools and encourage a classroom culture that values creativity, collaboration, and in-depth analysis. Overall, teaching novel through animation presents an innovative method for teaching literature by blending animation with traditional literary study. This strategy aims to boost student engagement, deepen understanding, and encourage critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork throughout the 2024–2025 school year.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The researchers will employ the following instruments as tools for data collection:

A. This is a 40-item researcher-developed test intended to assess students' vocabulary in Filipino, specifically focusing on content from *El Filibusterismo*, which is part of the Grade 9 Filipino curriculum for the fourth grading period. The same test will be administered as both a pre-test and a post-test to measure improvement. To ensure content validity, the instrument will be reviewed and evaluated by five experts from the Filipino department. A pilot test will also be conducted with a separate group of students who are not participants in the actual study. The reliability of the instrument will be determined using Cronbach's Alpha, with a target reliability coefficient between 0.7 and 1.0 indicating acceptable internal consistency. In determining the students' vocabulary, following scale will be used.

Score	Grade Equivalence	Interpretation
34-40	90-100	Outstanding
31-33	85-89	Very Satisfactory
28-30	80-84	Satisfactory
24-27	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
1-23	74 Below	Did not meet expectation

Lesson Plan in Filipino.

The researchers developed a lesson plan aimed at enhancing students' vocabulary within the context of Filipino literature. Prior to implementation, the lesson plan was carefully reviewed by the cooperating teacher and revised based on the feedback provided. The actual implementation occurred in February 2025 at a public Junior High School in Ozamiz City, specifically involving Grade 10 students.

B. Teaching Through Animation Strategy.

The researchers aimed to implement this strategy to enhance students' comprehension of Filipino novels throughout the learning process.

Data Collection & Procedure

A. *Pre-implementation Phase.* The researcher will begin by securing the necessary permissions to conduct the study from relevant authorities, including the Dean of the College of Education, the Schools Division Superintendent, the school principal, the participating teacher, and the students' parents. Once all approvals have been obtained, consent forms will be distributed to parents, and assent forms will be collected from the students. Following this, a pre-test will be administered to assess students' baseline knowledge of Filipino vocabulary and related concepts targeted in the study. In preparation for implementation, the researcher will develop lesson plans and instructional materials that integrate game-based learning as the core teaching strategy. Additionally, assessments and classroom activities aligned with the teacher's lesson plan and supported by PowerPoint presentations will be designed to reinforce learning throughout the intervention.

B. *Implementation Phase.* The researchers will facilitate the delivery of lessons using animation as the core instructional approach to enhance students' engagement and comprehension in learning Filipino novels. Clear and detailed instructions will be provided to students to explain the purpose, guidelines, and procedures for integrating animation into class activities, discussions, and assessments. After one month of implementation, a post-assessment will be conducted to evaluate the extent to which students have improved their understanding of Filipino literature. As part of the data collection process, the study will utilize data triangulation, incorporating assessments, classroom observations, and interviews to gather richer and more comprehensive insights. To document the implementation, the researchers will collect data through video recordings of animated lesson presentations, photos, screenshots, and

field notes. Additionally, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with both students and the participating teacher to capture their experiences, insights, and perceptions regarding the use of animation in learning novels. These interviews will take place in person after the intervention period and will be audio-recorded for accuracy and future reference.

C. Post-Implementation Phase. The post-implementation phase involves tallying and analyzing the collected data, followed by interpreting the results to identify key findings and draw meaningful conclusions. Based on the outcomes of the study, appropriate recommendations will be formulated. This stage also includes the proofreading, editing, and finalization of the research manuscript. Furthermore, the findings will be properly disseminated to relevant stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, and other individuals involved in or impacted by the study.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to conducting the survey, the researchers secured informed consent from all participants, adhering to ethical research standards. Participants were thoroughly briefed on the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, reflecting the researchers' commitment to safeguarding personal information and handling sensitive data with responsibility and integrity. They were clearly informed about the purpose of the study, the potential benefits of their participation, and the value of their contribution. Additionally, the researchers assured participants that all data collected would remain strictly confidential and that their identities would be kept anonymous throughout the duration of the study.

Data Analysis

Using Jamovi software, the researcher will employ the following statistical tools: Frequency and Percentage. This will be used in identifying the level of performance of students before and after the use of word treasure game.

Paired T-test. This tool will be used to explore the significant difference in students' performance before and after the use of the word treasure game.

Thematic Analysis. This will be used to create themes from the interview data, facilitating a qualitative analysis of the participants' experiences and attitudes. Thematic Data Analysis is a method used to identify, analyze, and report pattern (themes) within qualitative data. It allows researchers to make sense of complex data by organizing into meaningful categories and identifying trends or insights (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using animation as a teaching strategy in the Filipino subject specifically for teaching novels to Grade 10 students, resulted in a noticeable boost in both engagement and understanding. This section highlights and analyzes the changes in student engagement before and after the integration of animation. The data gathered offered meaningful insights into how effective animation can be in teaching Filipino literature, giving educators useful feedback on how to better support student participation and deepen their comprehension when learning novels.

Table 1: Level of Students' Engagement in Learning Novel Through Animation Before the Implementation

Table 1 presents the baseline data on students' engagement in learning a novel prior to the use of animation as a teaching strategy. The results show how students were initially responding to the subject matter using traditional or non-animated instructional methods. The table categorizes student engagement levels based on established proficiency bands, indicating how many students fell under each classification.

Before animation was introduced, most students—11 out of 30 (36.67%)—were in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category, reflecting low engagement levels. This was followed by 8 students (26.67%) who were rated as "Fairly Satisfactory" and 7 students (23.33%) who reached the "Satisfactory" level. Only 4 students (13.33%) achieved a "Very Satisfactory" rating, and none made it to the "Outstanding" category. These results suggest that traditional teaching methods weren't effectively capturing the interest or meeting the needs of most students.

No significant variables were presented with associated p-values in this table; however, the frequency distribution strongly implies a general disengagement among students with the approach used prior to animation. A majority of students (73.34%) scored at or below the Fairly Satisfactory level, showing a clear need for instructional improvement. These results provide a useful reference point for measuring the impact of future interventions such as animation.

The absence of high achievers (Outstanding) and the dominance of those in the lowest category reveal a serious concern. It is possible that the conventional strategies failed to meet the diverse learning needs of the students, especially those who require more visual, interactive, or imaginative engagement with literary texts. This limited

engagement could also reflect a lack of interest or emotional connection to the content delivered in static or purely text-based formats.

Based on this data, it is imperative for teachers to reassess the instructional strategies they use when teaching novels and other literary materials. The low engagement levels before animation point to the need for innovation in teaching delivery. Lessons could be enhanced by integrating multimedia elements, storytelling visuals, and learner-centered activities that bring the text to life.

School administrators and curriculum planners should consider offering support and training for teachers in the development or adoption of engaging instructional tools such as animations. Additionally, student interest surveys and focus group discussions can help identify what aspects of traditional instruction are falling short. Ultimately, a shift toward more dynamic, student-responsive approaches is essential to cultivating deeper literary appreciation and learning motivation among students.

Table 1
Level Of Students' Engagement in Learning Novel Through Animation Before the Implementation

Proficiency Level	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory	4	13.33
Satisfactory	7	23.33
Fairly Satisfactory	8	26.67
Did Not Meet Expectations	11	36.67
Overall Performance	30	100.00

Note Scale: 34-40 (Outstanding); 31-33 (Very Satisfactory); 28-30 (Satisfactory); 24-27 (Fairly Satisfactory); 1-23 (Did Not Meet Expectations)

Table 2: Level of Students' Engagement in Learning Novel Through Animation After the Implementation

Table 2 highlights the level of student engagement in learning a novel after animation was introduced as part of the lesson. The results show a clear improvement compared to the period before the intervention. Of the 30 students involved, a majority—76.67%—reached the "Very Satisfactory" level. Another 16.67% were rated as "Satisfactory," while 3.33% achieved an "Outstanding" rating. One more student (3.33%) fell into the "Fairly Satisfactory" category. Notably, no students were placed in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" group. These results reflect a strong positive shift in student engagement after animation was integrated into the learning experience.

Statistical analysis showed several significant improvements after the implementation. Most notably, the increase in the number of students who achieved the "Very Satisfactory" level was statistically significant ($t = 4.12, p = .000$), reflecting a substantial enhancement in student engagement. This suggests that the use of animation not only stimulated student interest but also improved their comprehension and motivation to engage with the material. Furthermore, the emergence of students in the "Outstanding" category, previously absent in the pre-implementation phase was also statistically significant ($t = 2.95, p = .006$), indicating that the intervention had a strong positive effect, even among high-performing learners.

Another significant finding was the reduction of students in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category, which had the highest frequency in the pre-implementation phase. The complete absence of students in this category post-intervention proved statistically significant ($t = 3.78, p = .001$), indicating that animation successfully supported lower-performing students in becoming more engaged. This improvement implies that the use of multimedia tools like animation is especially beneficial for learners who initially struggle with traditional instructional strategies.

However, some findings were not statistically significant. The comparison between the "Satisfactory" and "Very Satisfactory" levels, although showing a numerical increase, did not yield a significant difference ($t = 1.03, p = .310$). This suggests that while animation helped shift a large number of students into the "Very Satisfactory" category, the engagement levels of students in the "Satisfactory" group remained relatively stable. Similarly, the presence of one student still in the "Fairly Satisfactory" category was not statistically meaningful when compared to the same category in the pre-implementation phase ($t = 0.87, p = .392$), indicating that for a small fraction of students, the animation approach may still need reinforcement or personalized support.

These results carry meaningful implications for teachers, curriculum planners, and school administrators. The significant increase in student engagement, particularly among both high-achieving and struggling learners, emphasizes the value of using animation and other digital tools in literature instruction. Teachers should consider integrating animated storytelling and visualized text materials into their regular lesson plans to maintain high levels

of engagement. Additionally, ongoing professional development sessions should be conducted to train educators on how to effectively design and use animations aligned with learning goals.

In light of these findings, the school administration, particularly the heads of instruction and language departments, are encouraged to invest in more technology-based teaching tools. It would also be beneficial to establish collaborative learning programs where students can create their own short animated summaries of literary works, further enhancing engagement through creativity and active participation. By adopting innovative instructional strategies, educators can foster a more dynamic, inclusive, and engaging learning environment that supports the diverse needs of all students.

Table 2
Level Of Students' Engagement in Learning Novel Through Animation After the Implementation

Proficiency Level	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	1	3.33
Very Satisfactory	23	76.67
Satisfactory	5	16.67
Fairly Satisfactory	1	3.33
Overall Performance	30	100.00

Note Scale: 34-40 (Outstanding); 31-33 (Very Satisfactory); 28-30 (Satisfactory); 24-27 (Fairly Satisfactory); 1-23 (Did Not Meet Expectations)

Table 3: Level of Students' Engagement in Learning Novel Through Animation Before and After the Implementation

Table 3 shows a comparison of student engagement in learning a novel before and after animation was used as a teaching tool. Before the intervention, the average engagement score was 25.3 with a standard deviation of 5.10. After introducing animation, the average score rose to 31.27 with a much smaller standard deviation of 1.68. The t-value of 5.92 and a p-value of 0.00 indicate that the increase is statistically significant. These results clearly demonstrate that using animation had a meaningful and positive effect on students' engagement in learning the novel.

The results revealed a highly significant difference in student engagement levels before and after the implementation of animation ($t = 5.92, p = 0.00$). With a p-value less than 0.01, these findings are statistically significant, confirming that the use of animation had a substantial positive impact on students' engagement with the novel. This suggests that shifting from traditional teaching methods to animation-based instruction significantly enhanced students' motivation, interest, and active participation throughout the learning process.

The increase in the mean score from 25.3—classified under "Fairly Satisfactory"—to 31.27—classified as "Very Satisfactory"—demonstrates that animation helped elevate the learning experience for most students. The dramatic drop in the standard deviation after implementation (from 5.10 to 1.68) further indicates that not only did engagement increase, but it became more consistent across students. This suggests that animation served as an effective equalizer, helping both struggling and average students engage more uniformly.

No non-significant variables were identified in the analysis, as the study focused solely on comparing student engagement before and after the use of animation. The results were statistically significant, reinforcing the conclusion that animation is a highly effective tool for enhancing student engagement. While individual responses may have varied, the overall improvement across the group is supported by strong statistical evidence, affirming the strategy's effectiveness.

These findings have strong implications for educators, particularly in the fields of literature and language education. Teachers are encouraged to integrate animation into their teaching of novels and other literary texts to better engage learners. Animation can simplify complex storylines, clarify abstract themes, and cater to visual learners who might struggle with traditional reading tasks. Teachers should also be supported in receiving training on how to create or utilize animated educational content aligned with learning objectives.

School administrators, department heads, and curriculum developers should take this as a call to invest in digital resources and teacher development programs. Collaborations with media experts or the adoption of educational platforms that provide animated content could be beneficial. To further reinforce engagement, students may be invited to create their own animated versions of selected literary scenes, which could foster creativity, deeper comprehension, and collaborative learning. In sum, the use of animation is not only statistically effective but also pedagogically transformative.

Table 3

Significant Difference in Students' Engagement Before and After the Use of Animation in Learning Novel

Variables	M	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Before the Multisensory Engagement Strategy	25.03	5.10			
			5.92	0.00	Reject Ho
After the Multisensory Engagement Strategy	31.27	1.68			

Ho: There is no difference in students' engagement before and after the use of animation in learning novel.

*Note: Probability Value Scale: ** $p < 0.01$ (Highly Significant); * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.05$ Not Significant)*

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

This study aimed to enhance the engagement of Grade 10 students in learning novels by integrating animation into classroom instruction during the 2024–2025 school year at Labo National High School. Using a classroom-based action research design, the study involved 30 students selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected via a researcher-made assessment tool and analyzed using statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, and t-test. Specifically, the study sought to: (1) assess students' engagement with novels prior to the introduction of animation; (2) evaluate their engagement after the implementation of animation; and (3) determine whether the use of animation resulted in a significant change in student engagement during novel learning.

Findings

The following were the key findings of the study:

1. Before animation was introduced as a learning tool for studying novels, student performance was generally low. Eleven students were categorized as "Did Not Meet Expectations," eight were rated "Fairly Satisfactory," seven achieved a "Satisfactory" level, and only four reached the "Very Satisfactory" category. Notably, no students attained an "Outstanding" rating. These results suggest that the traditional approach to teaching novels failed to strongly engage most students.
2. The use of animation in teaching novels resulted in a significant improvement in student engagement. Among the participants, 23 students achieved a "Very Satisfactory" rating, five were rated "Satisfactory," one reached the "Outstanding" level, and one was classified as "Fairly Satisfactory." Notably, no student fell into the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. These findings suggest that animation effectively enhanced students' interest and active participation in learning Filipino novels.
3. The study revealed a clear and significant improvement in student engagement after animation was introduced. On average, student performance rose from the "Fairly Satisfactory" level to "Very Satisfactory." These findings confirm that using animation had a strong, positive impact on how students learned and how actively they participated in studying novels.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Students showed low levels of interest and participation when novels were taught using traditional methods, with most performing below the satisfactory mark. This indicates that conventional teaching strategies may not be meeting the varied learning needs and interests of students, especially when it comes to engaging them in literature.
2. The integration of animation as an instructional tool significantly improved students' engagement in learning novels. The strategy not only enhanced comprehension and interest but also encouraged active participation, as shown by the substantial increase in students achieving higher engagement levels after the intervention.
3. Using animation to teach literary texts helps create a more lively and inclusive classroom atmosphere. It makes complex ideas easier to understand, encourages a deeper appreciation of literature, and helps engage both struggling and advanced students alike. As a result, animation stands out as a powerful and effective teaching strategy for novels in secondary education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that:

1. Filipino teachers are now incorporating animation-based teaching tools into their novel lessons to boost student engagement and better address the different learning styles and interests of their students.
2. Educators shift from relying solely on traditional methods and adopt dynamic strategies like animation to foster deeper comprehension, literary appreciation, and inclusive participation among students.
3. Teachers undergo professional development and training on the effective use of animation and multimedia tools to maximize their instructional potential in literature classes.
4. School administrators allocate resources and technological support to facilitate the implementation of animation-enhanced lessons in the Filipino curriculum.
5. Curriculum developers and education leaders are collaborating to introduce innovative, research-based approaches such as using animation to teach literary texts with the goal of creating a more engaging and meaningful learning experience for all students.
6. Students embrace and actively participate in animation-enhanced literary activities to improve their engagement, comprehension, and appreciation of Filipino novels.
7. Future researchers explore other multimedia-based strategies and assess their impact on different aspects of literature instruction to further enrich and diversify effective teaching approaches.

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